

FLEXIBLE SUPERCAPACITORS BASED ON ALIGNED CARBON NANOTUBES WITH UNIQUE NANOSTRUCTURE

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Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, Supercapacitors, Energy storage, Ionic liquids, Nanostucture

ABSTRACT

Flexible supercapacitors were fabricated based on aligned carbon nanotubes as electrodes and ionic liquids as electrolytes. Different than randomly dispersed carbon nanotubes that were used for a flexible electrode matrix in the current literature, the flexible aligned carbon nanotube electrodes herein have a textured nanostructure with aligned channels that facilitates ion transport. Hence, high capacitance, energy and power were achieved. The capacitance is maintained at high charge/discharge current (50 mA), which can be attributed to the unique alignment of the nanotubes. Meanwhile, the electrochemical performances of assembled cells were not affected under bending mode, demonstrating the excellent mechanical support of aligned carbon nanotubes and highly flexibility of cell. To meet the real applications with different voltages and power, the cells were integrated in series. It could be found that stable electrochemical performances were obtained and the integrated cells could light light-emitting-diode (LED) bulb, demonstrating the potential applications.

1 Introduction

Portable and wearable electronic devices such as electronic paper, roll-up displays, mobile cellphones and sensors are highly desired and have developed fast in the last decades, which arouse the research interests for flexible energy storage devices [1-4]. Among various energy storage devices, supercapacitor has been considered a promising candidate, bridging the gap between battery and capacitor. It has the higher power density compared with battery and higher energy density than conventional dielectric capacitor [5-7]. Recently, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been reported to be the superior electrode matrix for flexible supercapacitor cells thanks to some excellent material properties such as high conductivity, high surface area, high flexibility and good electrochemical stability [3, 8-10]. However, the state-of-the-art works employing CNTs in flexible supercapacitor are mainly based on CNTs paper with random nanotube dispersion. Prior work has shown that the tortuous pathways formed from this configuration impede the ions transport, leading to the lower power and energy density [5, 11]. Alternatively, aligned carbon nanotubes (A-CNTs) can provide the aligned channel which can enhance the electrochemical performance of cell. Nevertheless, the as grown A-CNTs with low volume fraction (~1%) are not very stable to make flexible electrodes due to the weak interaction between the tubes in the bending mode. Here, in this work, we employed a unique method to fabricate highly flexible supercapacitor cell with an aligned and anisotropic nanostructure inside the electrode. The aligned nanostructure was still maintained after the one-step simple treatment with high flexibility. Based on this novel configuration, high conductivity and electrochemical performances of the as-assembled cell were obtained. It was found that the performance did not change under severe bending, demonstrating the high flexibility of the as-assembled supercapacitor cell. Moreover, the integrating ability of our cells was also investigated. The integrated cells exhibited stable electrochemical performance and could be used to power light-emitting-diode (LED) bulb.

2 Experimental

In this work, A-CNTs were grown via a procedure used in previous work [12, 13]. Briefly, small-diameter (~ 10 nm) multiwalled CNTs were grown by thermal catalytic chemical vapor deposition (CVD) on silicon wafers using a thin catalyst layer of Fe/Al₂O₃ deposited by electron beam evaporation.

Figure 1. The fabrication process and SEM images of the electrode [14].

Typically, CNT arrays with 1.6 mm height have 1% volume fraction (V_f) of CNTs with the average diameter of 8 nm in a CNT-forest (99% air). Then the CNT arrays were knocked down by a Teflon rod as shown in the Figure 1 following previously reported procedures [14]. P(VDF-HFP) was dissolved into DMF to form 0.5 wt. % solution. The solution was dropped on the knocked-down A-CNTs (KA-CNTs), or horizontally aligned CNTs film as shown in Figure 1 and put into vacuum oven so that the solution can infiltrate into the inside of arrays. The drying process usually took one day and the final thickness of the flexible film was around 150 μm .

The flexible supercapacitor was then assembled and a porous paper with 40 μm thickness was used as separator, immersed in solution of 2 M 1-Butyl-3-methylimidazolium tetrafluoroborate /Propylene carbonate (BMIBF₄/PC) used as the electrolyte. The electrochemical performance of the cell was evaluated by cyclic voltammetry (CV), galvanostatic charge-discharge and impedance tests on the equipment VersaState 4.

3 Results and Discussion

The SEM image of KA-CNTs/P(VDF-HFP) is shown in Figure 1. Based on the left image, the as-grown CNTs have very highly vertical aligned nanostructure and high aspect ratio. After one-step knocking down, the nanomorphology has changed to horizontal aligned which is beneficial to the flexible support. From the SEM image of the final as-synthesized electrode, it is obvious that the anisotropic and nanoporous structure is maintained after unique fabrication method. Those aligned channel, as well as nanoporous nanostructure can lead to the enhancement of ion transport. Hence, the electrochemical performances of as-assembled cells will be improved. The optical image of as-synthesized composite electrode as shown in Figure 2a exhibits highly flexible material property. The typical size of flexible electrode is 2 cm \times 2 cm \times 150 μm .

Figure 2. Flexible supercapacitor electrodes: (a) Optical image of flexible electrode. (b) CV curves under different scan rates. (c) Galvanostatic charge/discharge curves with different currents. (d) Calculated capacitances with currents

To investigate the electrochemical performance, CV measurements were performed under different scan rates of 5, 10, 20, 50, 100 mV s^{-1} from 0 to 2V for a two-electrode measurement system with 2 M BMIBF₄/PC as the electrolyte. As shown in Figure 2b, the cell shows a near rectangular shape CV curve, exhibiting an ideal capacitive behavior under 2V operation as well as a low internal resistance thanks to the unique horizontal alignment of the nanotubes in the flexible electrodes. To evaluate the capacitive performance of the cell, galvanostatic charge/discharge curves at different currents were also investigated. The symmetric charge/discharge processes shown in Figure 2c indicate the high energy storage efficiency. Based on the different currents, the cell capacitance can be calculated from the slope of discharge curves and the equation below:[15]

$$C=I/(dV/dt) \quad (1)$$

where I is the applied current, dV/dt is the discharge slope in the galvanostatic curves. The calculated cell capacitances with different discharge currents are shown in Figure 2d. The cell capacitance decreased from 0.22 F to 0.21 F as the discharge current density increases from 2 mA to even as high as 50 mA. This excellent capacitance retention with 95% can be attributed to the aligned channel formed by A-CNTs to ensure that the ions with high speed can still transport to the inside of CNTs at high current.

In order to evaluate the feasibility as a flexible energy storage device, the electrochemical performance of supercapacitor cell under bending state was performed and compared with that in normal flat state, shown in Figure 3. The bending angle with 90° (radius 1.25 cm) was created by wrapping the cell on a Teflon rod with diameter 2.5 cm. Based on the CV curves under 100 mV s^{-1} in Figure 3a and charge/discharge curves under 20 mA in Figure 3b, it is obvious that there are no apparent changes between the two states, indicating the excellent flexibility of the device. Figure 3c represents the charge/discharge cycling performance under different states. The cell was operated for 10 charge/discharge cycles under original flat state, then 10 cycles under bending state and finally recovered under flat state. Consistent with the data above, the mechanical bending did not change the capacitance much of the cell, showing that mechanical bending did not have significant influence on the ion transport in the electrodes thanks to the high strong mechanical support and flexibility of aligned CNT layer.

Figure 3. Device-level performance under strain: Comparisons of (a) CV curves and (b) charge/discharge curves of cell under flat and bending states. (c) capacitance cycling performances under different states. (d) Impedances of cells under the two states.

Impedance performance of the flexible supercapacitor cell under the flat and bending states in the frequency range of 100 kHz to 10 mHz at open circuit potential with a 5 mV perturbation signal is shown in Figure 3d. Similar with CV data, little change was observed under the two states. The sharp rise of imaginary part of impedance indicates ideal capacitive performance of the cells. By enlarging the Nyquist plots under high frequency range, the equivalent series resistance (ESR) can be found at the intersection between the curve and x-axis. Based on inset of Figure 3d, the flexible cell under two states exhibits very small ESR with 0.6Ω under the two states which is attributed to the intrinsic

resistance of the KA-CNTs. This small ESR leads to high conductivity of the flexible electrode and also explains why the capacitance retention can maintain as high as 95% under different discharge current as shown in Figure 2d.

Figure 4. Electrochemical performances of two cells connecting in serials. (a) CV curves under different scan rates. (b) Ragone plots describing the relationship between energy and power of the cells.

For real application consideration, portable and flexible electronics may need flexible power sources working at various operation voltages and powers [16]. Hence, the ability of integrating several cells using serial or parallel assemblies is extremely essential to meet those requirements. Here, we connected two cells in series to enlarge the operation voltage. Compared with single cell that can work under 2 V properly as shown in Figure 2b, the two cells connected in serials can be operated under 4 V with the similar CV curves displayed in Figure 4a. The energy and power can be calculated by the following equations[15]

$$E = 1/2 \times CV^2 \quad (2)$$

$$P = E/t \quad (3)$$

where C is the capacitance of cell, V is the operation voltage, t is the discharge time. The relationship between energy and power can be expressed in the Ragone plot in Figure 4b. It is obvious that energy of cell did not change much under different powers, demonstrating the excellent energy retention and electrochemical performances. As shown in the figure, the cell can be used to power the LED light. With the unique horizontal aligned nanostructure, the ions can transport efficiently under different powers, leading to the stable energy level and wide power range to meet various applications for portable electronics.

4. Conclusions

In conclusion, we have shown that A-CNTs can be employed as a promising flexible electrode matrix for flexible supercapacitor device after knocking down the A-CNT forest. Due to the highly anisotropic nanomorphology, the cell exhibited high conductivity, high capacitance and capacitive retention. Moreover, the performance changed very little under bending, indicating excellent flexibility that can be used for applications requiring flexible electronic components. The integration ability of cells was also investigated, and the flexible supercapacitor demonstrated herein based on KA-CNTs/P(VDF-HFP) nanocomposites has great potential in the wearable electronics.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by Analog Devices Inc. (ADI). Some experiments were performed through using of the core facilities at the Institute for Soldier Nanotechnologies at MIT by the U. S. Army Research Laboratory and the U. S. Army Research Office under contract number W911NF-13-D-0001.

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